

PARACHOR OF MERCURIC CHLORIDE

BY R. P. SHUKLA AND W. V. BHAGWAT

Parachor of mercuric chloride in water, in ethyl acetate and pyridine and also methyl alcohol has been determined. The low results in water indicate that mercuric chloride is appreciably ionised and hence is truly an electrovalent compound.

Bhagwat and Toshniwal (this *Journal*, 1942, 19, 493) have given results for the parachor of mercuric chloride in water and some organic solvents. The results are not consistent. It seems that the deviation is due to the fact that mercuric chloride is not very soluble in these solvents, and hence the molar fraction is very low. A slight error therefore is highly magnified. To get more accurate results we have used cathetometer reading up to 0.02 of a mm. for noting the height of the liquid in Jagar's maximum pressure method. Our results are more consistent and therefore more reliable and they are recorded below. x represents molar fraction of mercuric chloride.

TABLE I

Mercuric chloride in water.

Parachor of water as determined = 52.34.

Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
		$x = 0.003454$		
70.0°	1.020	64.04	52.42	81.25
65.0°	1.024	66.22	52.43	81.23
		$x = 0.007142$		
62.99°	1.064	62.99	52.53	88.62
63.0°	1.068	64.04	52.53	82.62
65.24°	1.073	65.24	52.54	84.05
		$x = 0.009545$		
74.0°	1.093	62.92	52.60	82.75
66.0°	1.096	63.54	52.62	85.90
66.0°	1.098	64.02	52.60	82.75

TABLE II

Mercuric chloride in methyl alcohol.

Parachor of methyl alcohol as determined = 88.81.

Temp.	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
		$x = 0.03556$		
22.2°	0.9991	26.50	92.06	180.4
25.0°	0.9942	26.16	92.23	185.0
30.0°	0.9900	25.67	92.12	182.0
		$x = 0.04498$		
20.2°	1.005	22.74	92.99	180.0
26.0°	0.9970	22.14	93.18	185.0
30.0°	0.9656	21.09	92.97	181.6

TABLE III

Mercuric chloride in ethyl acetate.

Parachor of ethyl acetate as determined = 213.2.

Temp.	d.	τ .	P_m .	P_x .
$\alpha = 0.07775$				
22.6°	1.088	25.23	210.6	180.0
25.0°	1.085	25.02	210.9	182.5
30.0°	1.079	24.63	211.0	185.4
$\alpha = 0.07318$				
22.3°	1.077	25.17	210.9	181.0
25.0°	1.074	24.84	211.0	183.0
30.0°	1.068	24.48	211.1	185.4

TABLE IV

Mercuric chloride in pyridine.

Parachor of pyridine as determined = 198.5.

Temp.	d.	τ .	P_m .	P_x .
$\alpha = 0.07206$				
22.1°	1.197	42.31	197.9	190.1
25.0°	1.192	41.59	197.6	186.2
30.0°	1.181	41.59	198.1	192.5
$\alpha = 0.7185$				
22.1°	1.199	43.01	198.2	192.5
25.0°	1.195	42.59	199.0	190.9
30.0°	1.195	41.59	197.3	180.0

The theoretical value for mercuric chloride is about 180. It will be seen that the value obtained in water is much lower, while in organic solvent the value corresponds to the theoretical, except in case of pyridine, where the value is somewhat higher.

Mercuric chloride is abnormal in its behaviour. Although it is an inorganic salt, it is more soluble in organic solvents than in water. Its conductivity at low temperature is low, but increases rapidly with temperature and shows an abnormally high temperature coefficient. Its coagulating power inspite of its low conductivity is very high, which indicates a high degree of ionisation in contradiction to conductivity results.

Since mercuric chloride is not expected to ionise in organic solvents, the results should approach the theoretical value 180. This has been found to be so. The high results with pyridine are obviously due to its peculiar behaviour in forming complexes of the type $HgCl_2 \cdot 2Py$, $HgCl_2 \cdot 4Py$, etc.

In a series of papers published from these laboratories (this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 53, 62; 1949, 26, 39) it is established that inorganic salts due to their ionisation show very low results. Conversely therefore, low results should be taken to indicate ionisation. Bhagwat and Tosniwal's results have failed to indicate any ionisation. We therefore have determined our value of parachor of mercuric chloride at higher temperatures and our results give low values of parachor than the calculated one and thus establish ionisation.